

Union with God in Christ

David Crews

Lincoln Christian University

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Dr. Trevor Cochell, Professor

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INTRODUCTION

Union with Christ stands at the very apex of the Christian doctrine of salvation. The whole of our personal relationship to God can be summed up in such terms. John Calvin agreed when he wrote, "*For we await salvation from Him not because He appears to us a far off, but because He makes us engrafted into His body, participates not only in all His benefits but also in Himself*" (Calvin, 1963, p. 34).

It is my thesis that intentional meditation upon union with Christ can enrich and deepen our personal awareness of God's incomprehensible, intimate love for us as individually, which can, in turn, significantly motivate us to trust, obey and love Him even more.

In 2007, when my faith was at its lowest point, and I began feeling a gnawing sense of God's remoteness,---I was drawn---providentially, I believe, by God's Holy Spirit,---to an extended time of sustained reflection on the sixth chapter of Paul's letter to the Romans. Day after day, for almost a year, I found myself being strangely incited, with no particular agenda, to meditate, for the first time in my life, upon this eye-opening, exposition of God's work in Christ, highlighting where we have been personally united to Christ in His death and His resurrection in deeply provocative ways. As a direct result of this meditation, on the Scriptural truths of union with Christ, it proved to be one of the most---indeed, perhaps *the most* significant---spiritually transformative leg of my Christian journey, thus far. Now, seven years later, I wish to revisit with collected insight from the Scriptures, biblical and systematic theology, the findings of key church leaders and theologians, and our contemporary cultural context, a deeper, even more panoramic vision of union with God in Christ.

If these goals are met, the following can be accomplished in this paper;

1. The concept of union with Christ will be taken from a symbolic metaphor to real experience, from sanctified theory to more a comforting actuality.
2. The teaching of union with Christ will be retrieved from a not-yet perspective to more the already-of-the-present view.
3. The truth of union with Christ will be redefined from the margins of academic theology towards the center of praxis in Christian discipleship, from the ancient, distant past reserved for mystical elite to more practical application of all Christians today, regardless of their spiritual stature.

Rev. Jeremy Walker, a pastor in Crawley, England makes this astute observation;

"For many immature or confused Christians today, a denial of basic spiritual realities [union with Christ] can become an excuse not to pursue those standards established for us in the Word of God. After all, we might ask, if I am not this how can I be expected to pursue that? So we cut the nerve of godliness and allow ourselves to live at a low ebb because we have told ourselves that we have no basis on which to expect anything different. Equally, we can cut ourselves off from the blessings and privileges to which we are genuinely entitled by our status in Christ Jesus, feeling ourselves unworthy of them (we are) and concluding that we therefore are excluded from them (we are not). Again, this polarizing effect is to deadness, leaving us and *feeling distant* away from God in Christ and despairing of any spiritual progress in godliness because of the mistaken assumption that we are somehow not in possession of the relationships or realities upon which that progress is grounded"(Walker, 2013, p. 7).

This point needs to be mentioned because it reflects the attitudes of so many Christians today; due to their lack of intellectual and spiritual understanding of their union with Christ, their expression of Christianity tends to be more *therapeutically deistic* or "*Romans 7-centered*." They may hear and see other Christians who seemingly enjoy a stronger relationship or greater joy with Christ, but they themselves operate from place of skepticism and ignorance of God's work in Christ. Many live in spiritual defeat and frustration due to their chronic bondage to sin.

Let us turn now to examine a doctrine dealing with the application for salvation, traditionally called "union with Christ," also known as "identification with Christ," "incorporation into Christ, "participation with Christ," or simply Paul's favorite, "in Christ."

Union with Christ stands at the center of Paul's articulation of the doctrine of salvation.

Indeed, one could say that the whole of our personal relationship with God is designated by this term. Moreover, union with Christ is theological shorthand for the gospel itself---a key image that pulls together numerous motifs in the biblical witness (McNeill & Battles, 1967, p. 31). Being in Christ is the essence of the Christian message and experience---union and communion. It is not overstating the case to agree with Lane Tipton, "there are no benefits of the gospel apart from union with Christ" (Tipton, 2007, p. 34).

"*What makes a Christian---a Christian?*" Most evangelicals would reply that being a Christian is a matter of "*praying a certain prayer*" or "*believing certain things*" to be true in order to "*accept Christ as Savior and Lord of their life.*" Of course we realize the importance of this, however, I would like to stress that what makes a Christian a Christian is *participation in the life of Christ*, or union with Christ. Our very salvation depends upon whether we are "*in Christ*" or not, according to (Ephesians 1). It is a *locative position* even more than a profession.

The words we use to describe being a Christian reveal our true theology. It is interesting to note Paul never used the word "*Christian*" to describe the followers of Christ. But, he did use a two-word phrase for our relationship with Christ that is found everywhere in his letters and almost nowhere in our churches today; *in Christ*. The expression "in Christ" (*en Christo, en kyrio, en Christo Iesou, en auto* etc.) occurs **216** times in the Pauline letters and **26** times in the Johannine literature (Demarest, 1997, p. 312).

One wonders why we don't talk about being in Christ or united to Christ any more than what we actually do. Perhaps, we are afraid it sounds a bit too archaic, too mystical or even a little too strange for modern usage. After all, we never hear the phrase used from the pulpit or a Bible study (as a Christian for the past 36 years I certainly have not). Furthermore, the last thing we want to do is embarrass ourselves by dropping this theological connotation in a conversation

while we are basically clueless as to its real meaning. So, we just choose to avoid the term altogether and stick to more "acceptable" descriptions of salvation we are more comfortable with. Yet, if it is true that we are "in Christ," *what exactly are we supposed to do that?* What practical purpose does it serve? Most Christians, yet again, would probably draw a complete blank, if asked. This is a sad reality which I hope will change in the church.

Perhaps there is another reason for this general silence. Maybe the *reality far exceeds the ability of human language to articulate it*. Maybe the task of understanding what it means is made even more difficult by the sheer limits of our humanity. Being united to Christ involves being spiritually connected, intimately, with the infinite Son of God, who Himself far transcends our finite being. Unfortunately, some mystics of the past, and a few today, tend to "romanticize" Jesus in ways which have little to do with Paul's teachings of being "in Christ."

45 years ago, theologian Lewis Smede asked another probing question that is just as relevant today as it was in 1970;

"How can a person who lived 2000 years ago radically change a human life here and now? How can Jesus of Nazareth radically affect us, as persons, to the depths of our being? How can He reach out over the great span of time that divides us from Him and change us so profoundly that we can become new creatures in Him? Does the Jesus of the past become, in fact, the Jesus of the present? The Apostle Paul says that He does! And this is the main difference between His influence and that of any other influential person. He touches us here and now, not merely by the ripples of the historic currents He once set in motion, but by entering into union with us personally. Union with Christ---this is the sum and substance of the Christian person's status, the definition of his new relationship to Jesus, the larger reality in which all the nuances of his new being are embraced" (Smedes, 1970, p. 7).

If all of that wasn't enough, Paul continues by saying that we are not only "in Christ" (2 Corinthians 5:17), but Christ is also "*in us*" (Ephesians 3:17; Galatians 2:20). Furthermore, Paul makes the astounding claim that Jesus did not die alone on the cross or arise from His by Himself---*we have been connected* to those history-shaking events with Him by God (Romans 6:1-4; Ephesians 2:5, 6). How ironic it is that most Christians who are baptized will hear these

words, "buried in the likeness of to the new life of His resurrection, "as they are lowered and raised in the water, but conclude this baptismal confession to be a *mere, symbolic creed* of the church, not a personal, transformative biblical reality which impacts not only everything we do and say, but how we say and do it. It defines our theology and all of its aspects: soteriology, pneumatology, eschatology and missiology. It not only organically connects the believer to Christ, but union with Christ serves as the live-giving, *spiritual umbilical cord* between and within the doctrines of biblical and systematic theology today.

Union with Christ reverberates within our hearts like a connective melody to heaven's music. The more we understand and embrace the nature of who we are now in Christ, our new identity, *the less* we will want to tolerate sin in our lives and *the more* we will want to praise God in our hearts. In fact, the main reason we sin now, in the first place, is because, in that moment of temptation, we experience a form of "*spiritual amnesia*" and forget who we are *now* in Christ. We forget we are living in the conditions of a "*new normal*" for our lives that has nothing to do with our attempts at being good, trying to impress God or religious endeavors, as sincere as they might be.

Though we enjoy a "new nature" of holiness with Christ, the *principle* of sin still remains within our fallen flesh and it seeks to deceive us by masquerading as if we are still "*in Adam*" when the truth is the bible emphatically teaches that God has *re-positioned* us to be now "in Christ." Moreover, while the principle of sin still exists, the power of sin has been crushed; its back has been broken. An authentic Christian simply cannot biblically, by his new nature, continually live in sin, because of the indwelling presence of the Holy Spirit and his or her consequent union with Christ. We may fall into the mud hole of sin, but we cannot categorically wallow in it, for the rest of our lives. (I John 3:6), "Anyone who continues to live in Him *will not*

practice sin. But anyone who keeps on sinning, as a practice, *does not know Him* or understand who He is." (James 1:23-24), "For if you listen to the Word and don't obey, is like glancing at your face in a mirror. You see yourself, walk away, and *forget what you look like.*"

That is why it is absolutely critical the Reformational doctrine of union with Christ be *retrieved and recovered* for our churches today, for it remains the single best reminder that the saving work of Christ is of no benefit to us apart from being *joined* to Him *personally*. Naturally, that is exactly the problem, according to Marcus Peter Johnson who writes, "in far too many evangelical expressions of the gospel, the *saving work* of Christ has been *so distanced* from the *saving personal* union with Jesus that it strikes us as rather *outlandish*."

We are more content to refer to the atoning *work* of Christ or the redemptive *work* of Christ on the cross as the basis for salvation. Yet, as *important* as such expressions are for a robust evangelical soteriology, there is an ever-widening fissure in Evangelical theology that threatens to *put asunder what God has joined together*" (Johnson, 2013, p. 16). The saving work of Christ is not to be thought of as an *abstract concept alien* to the living person of Christ, but a living reality that has both immediate and long term, beneficial consequences for practical, Christian living. Calvin said it this way, "as long as Christ remains *outside* of us, and we are *separated* from Him, all that He has suffered and done for the salvation of the human race remains useless and of no value to us. Therefore, to share in what He has received from the Father, He had to become ours and to dwell within us. For, as I have said, all that He possesses is nothing to us until we grow into one body with Him" (McNeill & Battles, 1967, p. 78).

Has contemporary evangelical soteriology somehow missed this *intensely relational* aspect of salvation---our personal solidarity Christ? Has this mysterious reality of our union with Christ, by which He dwells in us and we in Him, somehow fallen victim to the "over-

objectification of salvation?" Is there truly a dangerous dichotomy developing today? The verbiage of, "a personal relationship with Jesus," has been repeated time and time again, especially in evangelical churches. "Could it be that one of the reasons why American Christianity is deemed so superficial is because we are *confession heavy, but content lite?*" "Has the church done an adequate job actually explaining exactly what a *personal relationship* with Jesus is *really* all about, *outside of the fact that He has died for our sins?*"

It is interesting to note outside the Reformed tradition, the ideal of union with Christ appears to be largely undervalued. This has led to not a few theological observers to justly conclude, "At present, the majority of Christians much more frequently think of Christ as a Savior *outside* of themselves, then as a Savior who dwells *within* themselves, in spite of the teaching of the indwelling Holy Spirit. " (Demarest, 1997, p. 313).

Whether this "hole in our theology" is by conscious attempt or subconscious oversight, we would do well to take a step back and make every effort to recapture the richness of this doctrine as well as re-articulate *a more holistic* interpretation of *evangelical soteriology* which embraces both the *mystery and reality* of the church's union with its Savior. In (Ephesians 5:22-33), Paul is referring to about physical and spiritual oneness of marriage in Christ, this passage. However, in verse 32 he says, "This is a great mystery, but it is an illustration of the way Christ and the church are one." Paul is painting a picture here of the intimate union of "two becoming one." The key word here is, "mystery." Unfortunately, some pastors avoid teaching on topics that may seem too mystical for them to have all the answers. If that is true then, perhaps they have missed, " Now our knowledge is *partial and incomplete*, and even the gift of prophecy reveals *only part* of the whole picture!" in (I Cor. 13:9).

It is hard to deny a *subtle trend* which is putting unnecessary distance between the person and work of Christ. This is evident in our tendency to reduce salvation to rather abstract, extrinsic and impersonal terms. In textbooks, sermons and classrooms, salvation is often pictured as the reception of *something* Christ has acquired for us with *little emphasis* on receiving the *person of living Christ* in view of more relational elements of adoption and the new birth.

The gift of salvation overshadows the Giver of salvation, all too often. The gospel is portrayed as more a sanctified, philosophical offer of a depersonalized benefit, with little relation to Christ, (e.g. grace, justification, eternal life, forgiveness, etc.) rather than the gift of God Himself. Contemporary evangelical theology has rightly emphasized the saving work of Christ, but has also overlooked *the relational theology* through which we benefit from this saving work; our reality in union to the person of Christ. Instead of over emphasizing the benefits of Christ, we ought to be insisting that without Christ *in us* he can do nothing *for us*. This redefines salvation more as a personal relationship than a transaction. While we need not pit one against the other, as if this issue is an "either or" proposition. Careful biblical study reveals *both* the intimate relationship, as well as, the theology of union in Christ, both what God has done and with whom He has done this for. Reclaiming the doctrine of union with Christ could very well assist the church biblically balance the multi-faceted elements of the fascinating yet mysterious, biblical doctrine.

Such familiar phrases as "saved by grace" or "saved by the cross" can dissolve into creedal theological abstractions if pushed to the sidelines of the necessity of being personally united to Christ. Grace saves us only because we enter into it by being joined to Jesus Christ, who is the grace of God to us. The cross saves us only because, in our union with the crucified

Christ, we experience the benefits of His death. Jesus Christ is, in other words, the very content of both grace and the cross: *we are saved in Christ*, not apart from Christ.

J. Todd Billings, professor of theology at Western Theological Seminary is convinced, "the need for a renewed theology of union with Christ is made acute by at least two factors. First, the *functional or "lived"* theologies of salvation in the West have *deficiencies* in the precise areas where a Reformational theology of union with Christ has *strengths*" (Billings, 2011, p. 8). For example, many Americans "claim to be Christians," yet their personal conduct betrays a blatant contradiction. The ever so popular "*mega-church gospel*" is pre-packaged to appeal, not as a biblical theology of restored communion with God by grace in Christ, but more like a celestial benefits package to restore one's self-esteem, resolve emotional conflicts, revive failing relationships, improve one's overall outlook on life, heal diseases and fatten one's checking account. Against this popular, reductionist, gospel message, the absolutely, awesome God, personally encountered in union with Jesus Christ, is it once more breathtaking, majestic and more intimate than the deistic-tending God of the West.

I. Enigma of Union

"Now we see things imperfectly, like puzzling reflections in a mirror, but then we will see everything with perfect clarity. All that I know now is partial and incomplete, but then I will know everything completely, just as God now knows me completely" (I Cor. 13:12, NLT).

John Jefferson Davis, professor of systematic theology at Gordon-Conwell Theological Seminary writes,

"It is a peculiar and limited fact, then that in much of today's popular evangelical piety and preaching this great New Testament truth of union with Christ there appears to have *little traction and prominence in the understanding and experience of the gospel*. For many in the evangelical tradition, a tradition that speaks easily of a "personal relationship with Christ," a vivid sense that *already* we are now in living communion with Christ---not merely waiting to be united to Christ in heaven when we die---seems to be missing could this be a reflection of the pragmatic, activist temperament of much American evangelicalism, which tends to be suspicious of forms of spirituality that are

perceived as being "mystical" or "Catholic"? (Davis, 2012, p. 40)

Modern scholars and theologians, along with laity, have struggled to make sense of Paul's mystical language in union with Christ, being in Christ, crucified and raised Christ and being "seated with Christ in the heavenly realms" (Ephesians 2:6). One of the problems has been the fact there has been no *general consensus* on how to interpret these in these enigmatic, theological phrases of Paul.

Alfred Wikenhauser, a Roman Catholic New Testament scholar at the University of Freiburg, Germany, offered his provocative commentary on union with Christ as,

"Something real, an objective state that is true of all Christians without exception. It is a self-evident fact that as soon as a man becomes a Christian he enters upon this vital union with Christ. He is bound in a mysterious union of intimate fellowship in life and being. This union is not a fusion of two persons, but a union of Christ and the believer where each preserves his or her personality. It is an objective character of union with Christ for Paul because this fellowship with Christ is not a momentary experience which occurs at times of high spiritual exultation; it is a reality, an objective fact that does not depend on the perception of the operations of Christ. It is true, that these operations can be perceived but they are real whether we notice them or not" (Wikenhauser, 1960, p. 93)

E. P. Sanders, a prominent biblical scholar, recognizes the mystical or participationist dimensions of Pauline theology, especially in regards to the "in Christ" language which brings us closer to the heart of Paul's thought than do the legal or forensic categories of justification in Christ. Yet, in his best attempts to articulate this concept of reality---a real participation in Christ---he said, "I confess that I do *not* have a new category of perception to propose here"(Sanders, 2000, p. 520).

In this regard, James S Stewart deserves mentioning, "The heart of Paul's religion is union with Christ. This, *more than any other*, is the key which unlocks the secrets of his soul" (Stewart, n.d., p. 147).

II. Mankind's Universal Search for Union

Cultural anthropologists are now saying that it appears there is actually one common denominator all major religions of the world, since the beginning of time, have always agree upon; a deep desire to personally make contact and live in union with his or her God (McDaniel, 1992, p. 67). Understandably, all religions offer their own philosophical spin upon the nature of that union, and the way of attaining salvation. Yet, even in consideration of those religious nuances, it is quite plausible to argue that salvation is defined by some form of union with deity, regardless of culture, race, geography or historical era.

If this is indeed true, then the existential question every religion must answer is also the most profound question of human life, that is, *what is the way back to God?* Additionally, how can we be united with God, how do we experience the sharing of the divine, the eternal, with the mortal and finite nature of our own humanity?

Predating John Calvin's significant interest in and articulation of union with God, from the Reformed tradition, Christian theology is drawn to the Eastern Orthodox wing of the church, to their *doctrine of deification/and or union with God*. While the Eastern Church has predominantly carried this doctrine during the patristic era, the Western church, as we have seen, has also approached the ideal of union, but with a different linguistic identification.

The word "*deification*" comes packed with baggage requiring, interpretive special handling. The Greek fathers of the church understood deification to mean at the fall of humanity, man lost the likeness of God but retained His image, so that the Christian life is best conceived as the restoration of the lost likeness to those who have been redeemed in Christ. This, of course, is the work of the Holy Spirit, who communicates to us the *energies* of God Himself, so that we

may become *partakers of the divine nature* (2 Peter 1: 4). The energies of God come from His essence and share its nature; but it must be understood that the deified person retains his personal identity and is not absorbed into the essence of God, which remains forever hidden from his eyes. In actual practice, the Orthodox spiritual masters have tended to focus on the *attributes* of God which Protestant theology has called "*communicable*" so that there is a certain similarity between evangelical and Orthodox beliefs at this point. However, the Eastern churches have *never defined* the attributes of God in the way that the Western churches have done, so that it is impossible to equate the two doctrines exactly. This becomes particularly obvious in Protestant and orthodox views when the articulation of the image of God are compared; the standard Western view, that the image has been corrupted and even lost, finds no echo in Eastern theology, which is generally optimistic and its assessment of our fallen state, but without going to far as to deny the necessity of grace for salvation.

Deification corresponds most closely to the Western understanding of the *imitation* of Christ. In Orthodox theology, the Holy Spirit which proceeds from the Father rest on the Son and becomes His energies. We who are called to the imitation of Christ are likewise called to *manifest the energies* of the Holy Spirit, who, by adopting us as sons of God, makes assessable to us the spiritual power which belongs to Christ. In this way, we can fulfill what is prophetically seen in the biblical vision, that those redeemed by Christ *will be like gods* (Ps. 82:6) (Ferguson, Wright, & Packer, 1988, p. 189).

The universal search for union with God, the innermost longing of man's existence, has always been a driving force and leading motif of world religions from prehistoric times. For example, in Hinduism, death is the unsurpassed question and the goal is to temporarily ward off death in order to experience the ideal of deification.

Deification is looked upon as the means of death uniting the human being with God, rather than separating from the divine. Because of the cylindrical nature of the Hindu worldview, the human-God continuum is a circle rather than deification being the endpoint (Blackburn, 1985, p. 157).

From antiquity, the pages of history are filled with this concept of deification beginning in ancient Mesopotamia and continuing throughout the cultures of ancient Egypt, ancient Greece, ancient Rome, the ancient Incas of Latin America and the ancient Far East religions of China and Japan. But, we need not go very far back to the annals of our history to discover the same kind of inner, spiritual, undeniable desire today that has always existed. This becomes readily apparent in the popular manifestations of the occult, crystals, science, horoscopes, the Ouija board, modern paganism and various kinds of spiritism, as well as the New Age movement, the search for UFO's and the elusive Bigfoot phenomenon. These are all religious, spiritual pursuits which clearly testify to this intense, innate desire to experience the divine, the spiritual, on a personal level, regardless of the conscious awareness and realization from their followers.

This may explain the meteoric rise in the interest of spirituality today. Man cannot escape, try as he may, from this God-created, spiritual vacuum in his heart to personally encounter God on an intimate level of existence. The bread of materialism fails to satisfy his deepest needs, "*man shall not live by bread alone,*" (Matthew 4:4).

The challenge of Christian theology today is not only the effective engagement of gospel communication with other religions in our pluralistic world, but also with modern philosophical and scientific ideas that our children are being indoctrinated with beginning at a young age in our public schools and later in their college years.

The direction of this paper underscores the fact that, in spite of all the differences between world religions, and the East and West church tradition, there is a common motif to be found: *union with God*. Moreover, this union is made possible only in and with Jesus Christ, our Lord because of His redemptive work at this cross. Both the Eastern understanding of *theosis* and the Western ideal of *justification*, both have union with God as their ultimate goal. In a like manner, *the need for unity* among so many different churches today has never been greater. The splintering of Christianity into so many factions cannot possibly add to the strength of our witness. Thus, the ideal of union with God has profound implications not only with regard to Christian theology, but also for a Christian theology of religions.

It appears that the Christian church is hopelessly divided in terms of doctrines, politics, taste, leadership patterns, and so on. Most of all, every true disciple of Christ sincerely desires to know God better and experience His love and power in their daily lives. Regarding those outside the church, whether they realize it or not, they also have the same spiritual needs as those in the church.

Like it or not, all Christians, regardless of their particular tradition, are on their way and their spiritual journey, the very same salvation, provided by the very same God and Father of our Lord Jesus Christ. For the Christian witness to win the kind of contemporary credibility in an unbelieving and doubting world, we need a *more unified, consensual understanding of salvation*.

Some may say that it is just too naïve to hope for the church to be united in all of our doctrines. To a certain degree, that is entirely plausible. After all, the richness of Christian theology and witness is more like a *symphony*---not a *cacophony* of voices proclaiming the saving works of our Savior. The main issue here, however, is a fervent hope for a common

perspective on salvation that *emphasizes what we share in common* rather than what we differ on in minor theological details.

From the very moment of our supernatural, spiritual birth into God's family, by the saving grace of God in Christ, He implanted in our DNA the desire for a *twofold unity*; with the Trinity (Father, Son, and Holy Spirit) and with each other, as followers of Christ. This ever present yearning for union/communion with God and unity between other believers is the fulcrum strength of our witness. With that thought in mind, the question must be asked, "Could the doctrine of salvation, specifically in union with God in Christ, be a *possible catalyst* to build this unity that seems beyond attainment, in our era of ecclesiastical differences?"

Be that as it may, union with God is not only His greatest gift to humanity, but also the *ultimate goal* of human existence. It always been the prime consideration in the teachings on salvation from the early church fathers, especially in the East (Mantzardis, 1984, p. 12). Conversely, Reformation theology has wrestled with reconciling the idea of theosis with the doctrine of justification.

As a result, these two traditions have been considered diametrically opposed to each other. Eastern soteriology entertains problematic notions of the freedom of the will, too positive an anthropology, and, worst of all, the ideal of human-divine synergia in salvation (Karkkainen, 2004, p. 6).

Ecumenically, it is highly interesting and also a learning experience to be reminded of the fact that whereas for Lutherans the doctrine of justification is the doctrine upon which Christianity either stands or falls and the history of Orthodox theology there is almost a total absence of any mention of the ideal of justification by faith. Whereas Calvin described justification by faith as the "*hinge on which all true religion turned,*" the Eastern text, for

example the doctrinal manual of John of Damascus, *The Orthodox Faith*, never even mentions the idea (Clendenin, 1994, p. 37).

Contextually, when we look at Christian history, the church in the West focused on *legal* aspects of salvation, this is based on the *contextual* response to feudal society. In our postmodern society today, these images may seem a little strange since we are living in a totally different era. The Eastern Church has always lived next to the great Eastern cultures and religions in which the *question for immortality in union with the divine* has been the *dominant* concern. The West seems to lack a significant development in the notion of theosis. The Eastern Church neglects the concept of justification in favor of deification, a theme that it discovers throughout the Bible and repeats down through the centuries.

A striking new development, however, is happening today in ecumenical theology; many Protestants are now beginning a *rereading* of their spiritual heritage through the theological history of the universal church.

This includes reading our heritage through the Eastern orthodoxy strand of tradition. This exciting progress is yielding a re-reflection upon union with God in an effort to reclaim and reappropriate it as one of the oldest, if not *the very oldest* Christian symbol of salvation. Even the potentially polarizing word "deification" is being slowly being revamped by the word "*Christification*". This is based upon the idea that there is indeed a looming Christological structure to the human being in the destiny of humanity that is to be found only in Christ. Theosis is the mystery of human nature's perfection in Christ, not its alteration or destruction, because theosis is the mystery of eternal life in communion with God and the divine Logos (Wesche, 1999, p. 31).

III. Historical Interpretations of Union

A. Incarnational/Mystical union

As we have just seen, the Orthodox/Mystical tradition has historically stressed the incarnational foundation of our union with Christ as His taking of our nature, our flesh, at the incarnation where God in Christ becomes one with us in order to make us one with Him. Theologically speaking, the basis on which this whole process rests is that humanity was originally made in the image of God. However, sin defaced and marred this image to the point that is impossible for man to correct. Because Jesus Christ is the perfect image of the Father, it is only through Him that God's image is restored in us to by His incarnation and passion through the Holy Spirit. (2 Peter 1:4), "That you may *participate in the divine nature*, having escaped the corruption in the world caused by evil desires."

The process the person grows into a relationship with God which is ultimate we so intimate that it can only be described as union, according to the Orthodox Church. If human kind is to be what God intended in the creation, there must be a restoration of communion with God and the transformation of fallen humanity again into the fullness of the image and likeness of God.

The incarnation of the Word of God was the supreme act of restoration of the image of God in human kind. Orthodox Christians believe this transformation of human nature is something in which the believer in Christ *participates*, beginning at baptism. Those who have been baptized into Christ have "*put on Christ*" (Galatians 3:27). Through baptism we are brought sacramentally into an *ontological union* with Christ.

As the incarnate Son of God draws life from the Father, so those in spiritual union with Him participate in *His life-giving energies* (John 15:1-8). One of the big differences between

Orthodox union in Christ and Protestant union in Christ concerns their respective views of salvation. Protestants generally define salvation in *legal, jurisdictional or forensic* terms. Christ, in His death, paid the just penalty for mankind's sin. We receive salvation (forgiveness of sins) by virtue of our faith and His meritorious sacrifice on our behalf. While not denying the sacrificial aspect of salvation, *Orthodoxy* envisions salvation as transformation, the fulfillment of the image of God and humankind. The word used by the fathers of the church to denote this process was "*theosis*" or deification. Mystical union with Christ was said to involve experiences of ecstasy and rapture, suspension of human faculties and "an entrance upon a new order of life is so high and so harmonious with reality that it can only be called divine" (Underhill, 1930, p. 420).

According to the Orthodox tradition, the final stage of spiritual development is union with God. Ultimately the state will be the final experience of all believers in heaven. In the state of mystical union, consciousness of the act of prayer and even the words themselves fall away. All that remains is a union of love between God and the deified human soul. The light of Transfiguration that was seen in Christ on the mountain is now shared with us.

This mystical union is rooted in the mystery of the encounter of the spirit of man and the Spirit of God in Christ. It originates in a new birth brought about within a person by the Holy Spirit and centers thereafter on a life of healthy prayer, sustained meditation (based especially on God's word from Scripture), biblically-based contemplation and Christ-centered worship. The object of such biblically-based, spiritual disciplines is to deepen one's knowledge of the Lord, love relationship with Him and submission of one's whole life to God in complete trust and obedience. This is a *submission of love* in response to *God's love* the route to true wholeness of spirit and being. The ultimate Christian goal of *complete union* with the Lord, the unclouded

vision of God, has no precursors in pagan religions or occult practices. There is no loss of personal identity, as in the Buddhist-type of absorption into the infinite reality or universal consciousness promoted by Eastern mysticism. Biblical mysticism will always produce the fruit of the Holy Spirit and *increasing Christlikeness* in thought, word, deed and relationship both with God and with one's fellow man. An unselfish, sacrificial love (reminiscent of God's love in Jesus) marks true, spiritual mysticism. Mystical practices, however appealing or sincere, beyond the safeguards of Scripture, are to be rejected as they are undoubtedly deceptive and demonic in nature.

B. Sacramental union

The Catholic tradition has always laid great stress on the sacramental nature and means of initial and continuing union with Christ. Roman Catholicism tradition he claims that the church, headed by the Pope, is an extension or continuation of the Incarnation. Through the church, or the mystical body of Christ, the divine-human life of Jesus is channel to the world. Thus, "The Church is a sacrament, that is a sign instrument both of a very close knit union with God and the unity with the whole human race" (Kloosterman, 1972, p. 111).

Baptism, Rome claims, unites participants to Christ and to His body, the church, through the grace of regeneration. Moreover, the Eucharist unites participants most intimately with Christ and with other members of His body, the church. Based on the real presence of Christ in the Supper (Matthew 26:26-28) and the notion of eating Jesus is flesh and drinking His blood (John 6:50-57), Rome claims that Christians take Christ into themselves via a literal feeding in the Mass.

C. Covenantal union

Reformed theologians interpret union with Christ not as a discrete step in the *ordo salutis* but is a *comprehensive concept* that embraces the whole scope of salvation from eternity past to eternity future. Christians are united with Christ in a covenant relationship grounded on better promises and a sure foundation through His work on our behalf. The New Testament takes up the Old Testament theme of the covenant between God and humanity as the framework within which the Christian and the church in relationship with God through Christ is understood. This underlines the nature of the covenant union as one of committed mutual love; family-relationship pictures are also used as father/son, and the older brother and other children. Covenant theologians maintain that all people are *united with Adam* in the old humanity by virtue of his *federal headship* under the *covenant of works*. However, the elect are *united with Christ*, the second Adam, by virtue of His *federal headship* under the *covenant of grace*. This latter union of the saints with Christ comprehends every aspect of salvation from their election to the glorification.

The mystical union of Christ connected to His people is a concept that *transcends* all earthly analogies and all human understanding. *Objectively*, it was brought about by the Incarnation and atoning work of Christ. *Subjectively*, believers experience identification with Christ personally by operation of the Holy Spirit. As to its nature, union with Christ is *legal or forensic*, in that it determines the believer standing with God, together with all the privileges associated therewith. In the words of Kuiper, union "is both the fountain and guarantee of every Christian virtue and of every Christian exercise" (Kuiper, 1955, p. 39). This union is also *experiential* involving Christ indwelling one's life through His spirit, radically transforming personal character and relationships. It brings together every aspect of the plan of salvation, past, present, and future.

Union with Christ begins *before* the foundation of the world in the (1) *inception* of salvation whereas the elect are chosen by God from eternity. "There was no election of the Father in eternity apart from Christ. And that means that those who will be saved were not even contemplated by the Father and the ultimate counsel of His predestining love apart from union with Christ---they were truly chosen in Christ" (Murray, 1955, p. 165). Concerning (2) the *continuation* of salvation, union involves the establishment of fellowship with the risen Christ. By an actual partaking of Christ, saving grace, life, and power of the Savior become operative in the believer (Romans 6:4-11). This present aspect of union involves; effectual calling, regeneration, conversion, justification, adoption, sanctification, and perseverance. Finally, with respect to (3) the *consummation* of salvation, union involves the believer's bodily resurrection (1 Corinthians 15:22-23) and glorification (Romans 8:17) with Christ.

Union with Christ has its roots in divine election, it's basis and Christ's redemptive work, it's establishment with believers in time, and it's consummation in heaven. "Union with Christ was planned from eternity, and is destined to continue eternally" (Hoekema, 1989, p. 57).

D. Experiential union

Most evangelicals fit into this category and would view this interpretation of union with Christ as a discrete stage in the *ordo salutis*. It regards born-again believers union with Christ as a profound relation of *personal identification* and fellowship with the Savior. Inherent is the notion that the believer has died with Christ and his raised to new life with Him (Romans 6:3-11). Accordingly, the New Testament portrays the believer in Christ (John 14:20; Romans 8:1; 2 Corinthians 5:17; Ephesians 2:13; 1 John 2:6; 4:13), Christ in the believer (John 14:20; Romans 8:10; Galatians 2:20; Colossians 1:27), Jesus and the Father in the believer (John 14:23), and the Christian is a partaker of the divine nature of God (2 Peter 1:4). Concerning the *en Christo* motif,

en as a local sense; it describes the believer's new situation, sphere, or environment is transferred from the domain of sin to the realm of new, spiritual life. Union with Christ thus marks the end of the old existence in the beginning of the new (Elwell, 2001, p. 588).

This new reality is described as (1) a *supernatural* union effected not by human initiative but by the Spirit of God Himself (1 Corinthians 12:13; 1 John 3:24). The relation between the believer in Christ is not grounded in the nature of things, as is the relation between Adam and the human race (Romans 5:12-21). It is further (2) a *vital* union. In this new relationship with Christ, spiritual life and fruitfulness are imparted experientially to believers (John 15:2-7; Romans 6:11; 12:2; 2 Corinthians 4:16). Differing from Christian mystics, proponents deny that union with Christ involves a unity of essence between man and God. Rather, the human soul retains its unique creature qualities apart from its Creator and special individuality while being graciously energized by the Spirit. It is, moreover, (3) a *mysterious* union, in the sense that Scripture does not unfold the precise nature of the relation in union with Christ. We are given glimpses, images and metaphors for good reason; the reality of the concept is beyond our finite minds to comprehend completely on this side of eternity, especially. Paul described the relation between Christ and the church as a "profound mystery" (Ephesians 5:32; Colossians 1:27). In addition, it is (4) an *eternal and unbreakable* union (John 10:28; Romans 8:38-39). Finally, (5) the spiritual union between Christ and His people is both *individual and corporate*. It is a relation ensuing from the Spirit's operation in the believing soul and by extension "to all the saints in Christ Jesus," (Ephesians 1:1; Philippians 1:1; Colossians 1:2). As Shedd comments, "this union results from regeneration, not from creation. Consequently it is not universal, but particular" (Shedd, 1972, p. 534).

Incorporation into Christ first occurs as an *actual experience* the moment a believing sinner is made alive in Christ (Ephesians 2:5). Logically, the righteousness of Christ can only be applied to a person in union with the Savior. As Shedd comments, "the impartation of the righteousness of Christ *presupposes* a union with Him" (Ibid, 537)

Robert L. Dabney concludes that union with Christ assumes three forms; (1) *legal* as the imputation of Christ righteousness (i.e. justification), (2) *spiritual or mystical* as participation in the graces or qualities of Christ (i.e. sanctification) and (3) *social* as the communion of the saints. Yet this analogy does not infer the deification of believers, according to Dabney. The bond of the union is the indwelling Spirit, who cements together Christ and His people.

Moreover, the instrumental bond of the union is *faith*; obedient trust initiates and maintains this new relationship. The result of union with Christ is the application of full redemption to the sinner's soul (Dabney, 1972, p. 534).

In the humanity of Jesus, He underwent the full range of human experience in life, death and resurrection, in order to unite Christians with Him in the full range of His experience, calling and destiny. So close is this identification that Christians are said to be "*co-crucified*" with Christ and "*risen with Christ.*" Believers share His status, relationship and calling as sons and daughters of God, and are called to suffer with Him, to pass through physical death to ultimate physical resurrection, and reign with Christ in glory. Jesus has gone before us as our forerunner into the Father's immediate presence in heaven, thus the ensuring guarantee of the eventual arrival of all His people. In route to that goal, Christ calls all Christians into progressive conformity to His own image, continually renewing and transforming their characters into God's likeness by the power of His Holy Spirit within, and by the application of God's word to every department of their life.

Union with Christ is the working out of what God has worked in by the indwelling Spirit of God.

IV. Biblical Basis for Union

We have surveyed the mystery surrounding this doctrine and the various interpretations in church history of union with Christ, but the question still remains, "What does it really mean to be *'in Christ'*?" How can we better understand, with application to our personal lives, the Scriptural mandate to be *united with Christ*?" The limitations of this paper cannot possibly cover each and every instance of the vastness of this concept. Yet, we can get a more penetrating vision of just how every aspect of God's relationship to believers is in some way connected to our relationship with Christ.

As we have reviewed, "from the council of God in eternity past before the world was even created, to our fellowship with God in heaven in eternity future, including every aspect of our personal relationship with God in this life---all has occurred in union with Christ" (Grudem, 1994, p. 840).

John Murray adds, "Union with Christ has its source in the *electing love of God* the Father in the councils of eternity. Why does the believer entertain the thought of God's determined counsel with such joy? Why can't the believer have patience in the perplexities and adversities of the present? Why can he have confident assurance with reference to the future and rejoice in hope of the glory of God? It is because he cannot think of past, present, or future apart from union with Christ" (Murray, p. 164).

Union with Christ can be defined as follows: Union with Christ is a phrase used to summarize several different relationships between believers and Christ, through which Christians receive every benefit of salvation. These relationships include the fact that we are in Christ, Christ sent us, we are like Christ, and we are with Christ (Grudem, Ibid).

- 1. We are in Christ.**
- 2. Christ is in us.**
- 3. We are like Christ.**
- 4. We are with Christ.**

A. We are in Christ

1. In God's Eternal Plan.

Ephesians 1:4 tells us that, God chose us in Christ "before the foundation of the world." It was "in Christ" that we were "destined and appointed to live with the praise of His glory" (1:11-12). God "saved us and called us" because of "His own purpose" and because of the grace which He gave us "in Christ Jesus before the beginning of time" (2 Timothy 1:9).

Obviously, *before* the foundation of the world we were not born. Yet, these verses indicate that God saw into the future and knew that we would exist. It was His desire that we be in a special relationship with Christ, His Son. God did not choose us first and later decide to relate us to Christ.

Moreover, at the same time He chose us, He also thought of us belonging to Christ in a way that is indicative of being "in Christ." The point is that in the sovereignty of God, He chose us first to be "in Christ" *long before we chose Him*. In fact, had God not chose us *first* "in Christ" we never would have chosen Him. This *theological tension* in our union with Christ, between the sovereignty of God and the free will of man, must be maintained to be faithful to Scripture.

2. During the Life of Christ on Earth.

From the time of Jesus's birth to the time of His ascension into heaven, God thought of us as being "in Christ." Because Christ is our *personal representative* before God, whatever He did for us, God counted it is something we did, as well. The implications here are staggering. Though believers were not consciously present in Christ, since most believers did not even exist yet when Christ was on earth, believers were present in Christ *only in God's thoughts*. God thought of us is going through everything that Christ went through, because Jesus is our personal representative.

This means that when Jesus perfectly obeyed God for His whole life, God thought of us as having obeyed, too. "By one man's obedience many will be made righteous (Romans 5:19). Christ as our source of righteousness (1 Corinthians 1:30; Philippians 3:9). Because God thought of us as being "in" Christ, He also could think of our sins as belonging to Christ, "God made Him who had no sin to be sin for us" (2 Corinthians 5:21), and "the Lord has laid on Him the iniquity of us all" (Isaiah 53:6). Interestingly enough, these were sins we had not yet committed, but God knew about them in advance, and thought of them as belonging to Christ, ahead of time. "He Himself bore our sins in His body on the tree" (1 Peter 2:24).

However it was not just our sins that God thought of as belonging to Christ, it was ourselves. When Christ died, God thought of us as having died. Our old self was "crucified with Him" (Romans 6:6). "I have been crucified with Christ" (Galatians 2:20). "One has died for all, therefore all have died" (2 Corinthians 5:14; Romans 6:4-5, 8; 7:4; Colossians 1:22, 2:12, 20; 3:3; 2 Timothy 2:11).

In a like manner, God thought of us as having been buried with Christ, raised with Christ and taken up to heaven with Christ in glory. "God raised us up with Christ and seated us with Him in the heavenly realms in Christ Jesus" (Ephesians 2:6; Colossians 2:12-13). When Christ returned to heaven, therefore all the blessings of salvation were earned for us. God thought of those blessings as being rightfully ours, just as if we had earned them for ourselves. They were stored up for us in heaven---in God's mind, actually, and in Christ, our representative---waiting to be applied to us personally (1 Peter 1:3-5; Colossians 3:3-4; Ephesians 1:3).

3. During Our Lives Right Now

Once we have been born, and exist as real people in the world, our union with Christ can no longer be something just in the mind of God.

We must be brought into an actual relationship with Christ through which the benefits of salvation can be up tied to our lives by the Holy Spirit. Our present life in Christ can be viewed from four slightly different dimensional perspectives:

- 1. We have died and been raised with Christ.**
- 2. We have new life in Christ.**
- 3. All our actions can be done in Christ.**
- 4. All Christians together are one body in Christ.**

a. Dying and Rising with Christ: The death, burial, and resurrection of Jesus now have real effects in our lives today. "You were buried with Christ in baptism, in which you were also raised with Christ through faith in the working of God, who raised Him from the dead" (Colossians 2:12). Here Paul's references to baptism and faith indicate that are dying and rising with Christ occur in this present life, at the time we become Christians.

Paul sees this present death and resurrection with Christ as a way of describing and explaining the *transformational change* the Holy Spirit brings about in our character and personality when we become Christians. The Holy Spirit *reproduces* Jesus's death and resurrection when we become Christians, when we believe in Christ. This *metamorphosis* change of the new birth motivates us to become *so unresponsive* to the bondage, attractions and desires of our previous, sinful way of life, that Paul can say we are "*dead*" to these influences, because we have died with Christ (Romans 7:6; Galatians 2:20; 5:24; 6:14; Colossians 2:20).

Furthermore, from the positive side, the Holy Spirit *literally* changes our affections and motivates us to want to serve God, coupled with the supernatural ability we did not have before, with far greater power and success, so much so that Paul says we are now "alive" to God, because we have been *raised* with Christ: "We were buried therefore with Christ by baptism into death, so that as Christ was raised from the dead by the glory of the Father, we too might *walk in newness of life* (Romans 6:4).

"So you must also consider yourselves dead to sin and alive to God in Christ Jesus" (Romans 6:11; 1 Peter 1:3; 2:24). Because we died and rose with Christ, we have real supernatural power to overcome personal sin more and more, which reflects *progressive growth* (Romans 6:12-14, 19); we have come to "*fullness of life*" in Christ (Colossians 2: 10-13). This radical change is *so phenomenal, so dramatic* that it can only be called a "new creation" in Christ (2 Corinthians 5:17). Because of this, we should therefore set our minds on things that are above, where Christ is (Colossians 3:1-3).

b. New Life in Christ: We are to think not *only* in terms of what Christ has done in the *past* for our redemption, but also in terms of *His present life in heaven*, and *His continuing possession* of all the spiritual resources we need to live the Christian life. Because *every* spiritual blessing was earned by Christ and belongs to Christ, the New Testament can say that these blessings are "in Him." Therefore, they are available only to those who are "in Christ" and if we are in Christ, these blessings are ours. John writes, "God gave us eternal life, and this life is in His Son" (1 John 5:11), and Paul speaks of "the promise of the life which is in Christ Jesus" (2 Timothy 1:1). We read that "in Christ" are "faith and love" (1 Timothy 1:14; 2 Timothy 1:13), "grace" (2 Timothy 2:1), "salvation" (2 Timothy 2:10), "all the treasures of wisdom and knowledge" (Colossians 2:3), and God's "riches in glory" (Philippians 4:19), and Paul says that it is because of God's work that Christians are "in Christ who God made our wisdom, our righteousness and sanctification and our redemption" (1 Corinthians 1:30), and that "God has blessed us in the heavenly realms with every spiritual blessing in Christ" (Ephesians 1:3).

Every stage of the application of salvation is given to us because we are "in Christ." Our salvation, regeneration, justification, resurrection, glorification---our lives are inseparably connected to Christ Himself, the Holy Spirit gives us all the blessings of Christ is earned.

c. All Our Actions Can Be Done in Christ: The tremendous, paradigm shift of change within our lives are also accompanied by transformation in the realm in which we live. The Christian has entered the newness of the age to come, and has experience, to some degree, the new powers of the kingdom of God affecting every part of our lives. To be "in Christ" is to be a part of that new realm that Christ controls.

This means that every action in our lives can be done "in Christ," if it is done in the power of His kingdom and in a way that brings honor to Him. For example, Paul speaks the truth "in Christ" (Romans 9:1), is proud of his work "in Christ" (Romans 15:17), reminds the Corinthians of his ways "in Christ" (1 Corinthians 4:17), hopes "in the Lord Jesus" to send Timothy to Philippi (Philippians 2:19), rejoices greatly in "the Lord" (Philippians 4:10), and "in the Lord" commands, besieges and exhorts other Christians (1 Thessalonians 4:1). Paul says, "I can do all things in Christ who strengthens me" (Philippians 4:13). Paul's hope for Christians is that they live in Christ, "Just as you receive Christ Jesus as Lord, continue to live in Him, rooted and built up in Him" (Colossians 2:6-7). There are countless other verses Paul writes using the same reference of "in Christ." Everything that we do, should be done "in Christ" because of our union in Him.

d. One Body in Christ: In Christ, we are simply *not isolated individual* persons. All who are in union with Christ are also related to one another in His body. We are members of one another (Romans 12:5; 1 Corinthians 10:17). In this body of Christ, the worldly criteria status no longer applies, "There is neither Jew nor Greek, there is neither slave nor free, there is neither male nor female; for you are all one in Christ Jesus" (Galatians 3:28; Ephesians 2:13-22). According to (1 Peter 2:4-5), believers are said to be like living stones, built into a spiritual house, unified and

forever depended on one another, just as stones of a building are united to each other and depended upon each other, for the whole structure of the building.

The most graphic analogy of all is made by Jesus, who prays for believers "that they may all be one; even as You, Father, are in Me, and I in You, that they also may be in Us" (John 17:21). Jesus prays that our unity would be like the perfect unity between the Father and the Son in the Trinity.

B. Christ in Us

It is not only true that we are in Christ; He is also in us, to give us *power* to live the Christian life, "I have been crucified with Christ; it is no longer I who live, but Christ who lives in me" (Galatians 2:20). The identifying factor that determines whether someone is a Christian is whether Christ is in him (Romans 8:10; 2 Corinthians 13:5; Revelation 3:20). Thus, Paul can tell his Gentile readers that God's mystery is "*Christ in you, the hope of glory*" (Colossians 1:27).

It is paramount to maintain, on the basis of biblical testimony, that there is a *real, personal, dynamic dwelling of Christ in us*, and that this does not mean that we merely agree with Christ or that His ideals are in us. Rather, *He is in us and remains in us* through faith (Ephesians 3:17; 2 Corinthians 13:5). To overlook this truth would be to neglect the great source of *spiritual strength* that we have within us (1 John 4:4). *To remember this* works well to destroy our sinful pride, gives us a constant feeling of deep dependence on Christ, and gives us great confidence, not in ourselves, but in Christ working in us (Romans 15:19; Philippians 4:13).

C. We Are Like Christ

A third aspect of union with Christ is our imitation of Him, "Be imitators of me, as I am of Christ," writes the apostle Paul in (1 Corinthians 11:1). John reminds us, "He who says he abides in Him ought to walk in the same way in which He walked" (1 John 2:6). So union with

Christ implies that we should imitate Christ. Our lives ought so to reflect what His life was like that we bring honor to everything we do (Philippians 1:20).

Our imitation of Christ is especially seen in our attitude toward *suffering*. One of the great deficits in much of today's preaching is the deliberate omission of the fact that Jesus promised there would be suffering in the Christian life.

Christians are called to take suffering *patiently*, "because Christ also suffered for you, leaving you an example, that you should follow in His steps" (1 Peter 2:21). Paul's goal is to "share Christ's sufferings, becoming like Him in His death" (Philippians 3:10).

Our suffering is connected to sharing Christ's glory when He returns, "We suffer with Him in order that we may also be glorified with Him" (Romans 8:17). This is probably because it is through suffering and difficulty that God *makes us more like Christ* and causes us to grow to maturity in Christ (James 1:2-4; Hebrews 5:8-9). It should give us great comfort to know that we are only experiencing what He has *already experienced*, and that He therefore perfectly understands what we are going through, and listens sympathetically to our prayers during suffering (Hebrews 2:8 teen; 4:15-16; 12:11).

D. We Are With Christ

1. Personal Fellowship with Christ.

Union with Christ allows us to *interchangeably* use the phrase we are with Christ or crisis thus since both phrases mean the same thing. "I am with you always, even to the close of the age" (Matthew 28:20). Perhaps we have grown *contemptible* with the familiarity of these precious promises. We must not, however. This is the awesome Creator of heaven and earth who is promising His divine personal presence in Christ. In some sense, which *transcends our comprehension*, when we unite in worship we actually entertain the *sacred space* of some

dimension of heaven "to innumerable angels, and to the assembly of the firstborn who are enrolled in heaven, and to a Judge who is God of all, and to the spirits of just men made perfect, and to Jesus, the mediator of a new covenant" (Hebrews 12: 22-24).

(Hebrews 12) infers the "communion of saints" whether or not we are consciously aware of being in the presence of this heavenly assembly, there's a good chance that they may be able to witness our worship and rejoice in it. Without question, there is a *joy dimension* of heaven that we are aware of in our union with Christ in worship.

2. Union with the Father and Holy Spirit.

Because we are in union with Christ, we are also brought into union with the Father and with the Holy Spirit. With the Father (John 17:21; 1 Thessalonians 1:1; 2 Thessalonians 1:1; 1 John 2:24; 4:15-16), and with the Holy Spirit (Romans 8:9; 1 Corinthians 3:16; 6:19; 2 Timothy 1:14).

V. Selected Doctrines Engaged with Union

The English Puritan, nonconformist pastor, Rev. Thomas Watson, who was permanently ejected from his church in 1662, once wrote in his treatise, *The Mystical Union of Believers with Christ*, "In order to seek one's interest in eternal life, and partake of those blessings which are given forth by Christ, it is of *absolute necessity, that we be united to Christ*. If we will have life from the Son, we must have the Son; that is, we must be made one with Him no union with Jesus, and no communication of life and salvation from Jesus. First the Lord doth plant believers into Christ, and then bless them in Him and through Him" (Stedman, 1668, p. 335)

Union with Christ and Justification

According to Paul in (Romans 5:12-21), just as Adam plunged the whole race into sin and death because of their relationship of solidarity with him, so the second Adam (Christ Jesus) brings life and righteousness to all who sustain a relationship of solidarity with Him.

"If, because of one man's trespass, death reigned through that one man, much more will those who receive the abundance of grace and the free gift of righteousness reign in life through one Man, Jesus Christ. (Romans 5:17, ESV). Justification is received only by faith and is grounded on what Christ did for all in His death and resurrection (4:25). Paul's point is that we are not addressed merely as discrete individuals; instead we are placed by God in solidaristic groups or teams. Adam was head of a team, or team leader, of which we were all made part of even before our birth, if for no other reason because he was our federal representative per God. Originally, it was his sin which plunged the whole team of humanity into sin, death and condemnation. If anything, we mirrored what he did initially in the Garden. Despite this theological fact of our fallenness, what Christ did for us, at the cross and in His resurrection, was also done as the head of a team of which we are also an integral part per God. As Adam did on our behalf, much to our undoing, in a like manner, Jesus did the "*undoing of our undoing*"---on our behalf---for us, and God considers it or credits this redemptive work to our spiritual account as a result of being united, through faith, with Christ as the head of our team of humanity. Our *justification* is therefore *grounded* in our union with Christ (Garcia, 2006, p. 61).

Union with Christ and Sanctification

As I mentioned in the beginning of this paper, regarding the Spirit's directing of my meditative attention to (Romans 6), in this chapter of the book of Romans, it is written from a context in answer to the charges that Paul's gospel encourages moral indifference. Without hesitation, the great apostle straightforwardly insists that all true believers, the justified, live for

Christ and do not give themselves over to sin. Nor, do they use the grace of God as a license to sin. Why is this so? This is precisely because they participated in the death with Christ. They died with Christ to sin and rose again to new life in His resurrection.

And yet how many believers today question these truths, their applicability to postmodern living, much the same as one might pursue attempting the futile "action of nailing Jell-O to the wall.?" God seems "out there somewhere," not "up close and personal" in their lives. They struggle to make sense of their walk with God, trying to fight sin in their inconsistent, futile efforts from the flesh. Many churchgoers eventually become so frustrated or disappointed with God that they leave church altogether.

Nevertheless, the overwhelming weight of Scriptural evidence indicates Jesus Christ not only died and rose again *for* believers, but they also died and rose *with* Him, as well. This makes union with Christ the foundational basis for sanctification and the dynamic force that empowers the believer with the spiritual energy necessary to overcome the tyranny of the slavery of their own sins. "Do you not know, that is many as were baptized into Christ Jesus, were baptized into His death; we were buried with Him through baptism into death, so that as Christ was raised from the dead to the glory of the Father, so we too should live in newness of life (Romans 6:3-4).

Union with Christ and Resurrection

Along with our justification and sanctification, Paul makes the persuasive argument in (1 Corinthians 15) that the resurrection of Christ and the future resurrection of His church is one reality (vvs. 12-19). Paul argues back and forth from one to another. If Christ is not raised, there can be no resurrection of believers. If there is no general resurrection Christ cannot have been raised Himself. The two stand together. In fact, Christ has been raised---and so, therefore we will too. Christ is the first fruits of the resurrection of believers at His return (vv. 19-23). Hence, it is

an iron clad guarantee that not only will the full harvest will be gathered, but that both His resurrection and our resurrection are *identical*.

From this fabulous theological truth, it should be clear that the resurrection of believers at the Parousia is a resurrection *in Christ, not apart from Christ or as an additional sideline eschatological event*. Interestingly enough, the Einstein-Bell-Podorsky theory of the identical behavior of subatomic particles separated by indefinite space is paralleled here in the resurrection (Letham, 2011, p. 7). The resurrection of Christ and the resurrection of the righteous in Him, separated by indefinite time, are identical because the latter occurs in union with the former. Or, in other words, where Jesus is we are too, because of our intimate connection to Christ. Likewise, Paul's rhetorical question; Can *anything* separate us from Christ's love? (Romans 8:35) takes on a compelling, new meaning, in consideration with our union in Christ, the union of God's eternal love for us in Christ.

It must be emphasized that the resurrection Paul is talking about right here, "For God raised us from the dead *along with Christ*," (Ephesians 2:6) does not refer to our physical, future resurrection, but to our being *spiritually raised with Christ in the past*, to being "co-resurrected" with Christ (Snodgrass, 1996, p. 100). Paul portrays our future, physical reference in many other passages elsewhere in his epistles.

The exact "*how we are raised up*" methodology is not explained by Paul. Yet, one thing is for sure, physical resurrection is not meant here, but this spiritual, co-resurrection is very real nonetheless. If humanity's plight is a *living spiritual death* (2:2-3), the only solution is a *living spiritual resurrection*. Life must be infused and that life must be *divine life*, God's very own organic, *Zoe life*, which is the only dimensional quality of life powerful enough to triumph completely over our mortal, spiritual death condition so plaguing mankind.

The Holy Spirit is the One who makes the dead live, according to Scriptural testimony, "Under the new covenant, the Spirit gives life" (2 Corinthians 3:6), "the Spirit alone gives eternal life. Human effort accomplishes nothing," (John 6:63). The Spirit is the appointed divine *Resurrector* from God as God, in union with the Father and Christ, the Son. Salvation depends on both the resurrection and the death of Christ. When we believe, we actually participate in the *twin event* of the death and resurrection of Jesus.

Union with Christ and Ascension

"And God has raised us up together, and made us sit together in heavenly places in Christ Jesus" (Ephesians 2:6). As outlined above, we have not only been raised with Christ, but because of our union with Christ, we are also seated with Christ in the heavenly realms. This means that what is true of Him is comparably true of us. As fantastic as this sounds, it is our new reality. If Jesus is exalted to God's right hand---so are we. We are joined to Him so much so that we are where He is. Related texts that also speak of being exalted with Christ include (Romans 8:37, 1 Corinthians 15:48, 2 Corinthians 2:14, Galatians 4:26, Philippians 3:20, Colossians 3:4-4), but no text states this idea quite as forcefully as here in (Ephesians 2:5-6). Paul's purpose is to underscore the *exalted life believers now enjoy* as their new reality with Christ, and with that life comes privilege, honor, security and responsibility.

We recognize the fact that this is not, however, the same as saying we are actually seated in heaven right now. The "*heavenly realms*" is not merely a synonym for "heaven." The phrase points to the heavenly---i.e. the spiritual---reality of God and His work in Christ. Leon Morris suggests "the realm of spiritual realities" (Morris, 1972, p. 59).

The "heavenly realms" are not separated from this world; on the contrary, they are *determinative* for this world. This is the essence of being "in the world, yet not of the world," in our Christian witness to the world.

It is critical that we not miss this point; being raised with Christ and being seated with Him are conditioned on being "*in Christ Jesus*" or otherwise, in union with Christ. It is imperative that we "*rehearse our spiritual script*" and understand that being in Christ is not only the fundamental fact of the individual Christian's existence, it is the whole reality upon which we must build our entire lives upon in order to experience the blessings God has available for us as those who have been co-crucified, co-resurrected and co-seated with Christ.

As far as Paul is concerned, both the death and resurrection of Christ are *not merely* historical events which produce the salvation benefit for believers, they are events which all true believers *participate in, connected and joined to* and are included in, accordingly. All of this points to Paul's latent concept of "*spheres of influence*" from a theological standpoint. To put a finer point to this; it is a matter of the question of to whom one will serve. There only two options; we may choose to serve the tyrant of sin or the Savior, the Lord Jesus Christ. By default, and because of our solidarity with Adam, we come into this world already chained to this tyrant of sin.

However, conversion is the *radical transfer of ownership* from one sphere to the other, a change of lordships, and being raised with Christ is the theological language Paul uses to describe the spiritual transfer from the realm of death to the realm of life. In a short of such a theology fails to understand Paul, and for that matter, the fundamental theme to the entire New Testament of being "in Christ," which is shorthand for being in union with Christ.

As Tony Lane has written, "Until we are united with Christ what He has achieved for us helps us no more practical than an electricity main supply which passes our house but is not connected to it" (Lane, 2002, p. 23).

Union with Christ and Creation

Union with Christ relates to Genesis because it points to God the Creator is a *relational* being, with man-made in His image reflecting this characteristic in Himself. Ultimately, it points for to the coming of Jesus Christ, who is the perfect image of the invisible God.

The first chapter of Genesis portrays the creation and formation of the world, and the *ordered shaping* of a place for the human race to live. It presents man as head of creation, in relation to an in communion with God is Creator. This God who created the universe does not work in a monolithic way. His order is varied---is threefold but one. His work shows diversity and its unity and unity in its diversity. This God loves order and variety together.

The triadic manner of the Earth's formation reflects who God its Creator actually is; He is a relational being. This is implicit from the very start. With the creation of man is the unique deliberation "Let us make man in our image," which expresses plurality in God (vv. 26-27). Since Scripture has a fullness that often goes beyond the horizons of the original author's, the many church fathers who saw this is a reference to the Trinity were certainly on the right track. The New Testament gives us the principle that the Old Testament contains in seed form what is more fully made known in the New Testament, and on that basis with a look back to the earlier writings, much as at the end of a detective mystery we reread the plot, seen clues that we missed the first time but are now given fresh meaning by our knowledge of the whole. In terms of the *senus plenior* (the "fuller meaning") of Scripture, these words of God attest a plurality in God, which later came to be expressed in the doctrine of the Trinity (Wenham, 1987, p. 15).

When we look at (Genesis 1:26-27), we see that man exists as a duality, the one in relation to the other, as for God Himself the context points to His *own intrinsic relationality*. This relationality will be developed in the corpus of biblical revelation eventually and the disclosure taking form in the concept of tri-unity. Union with Christ rests upon the foundation of *man's nature as created*, seen in the light of God's and purpose for man. Christ as the second or last Adam a cheese what the first Adam failed to do. And for this, the incarnation of Christ is crucial and is the next place we will turn in our journey of union with Christ.

Union with Christ and Incarnation

In our previous discussion, with the Eastern Orthodox tradition, we surveyed their emphasis on the incarnational aspect of union with God. I would like to offer some further details in a zoom lens approach to the finer points of this topic. Briefly, according to the teachings of the New Testament, Christ has completely identified Himself with us. He is one with us. He everlastingly took our nature into personal union. He is at the Father's right hand in our flesh. The incarnation is the indispensable basis for union with Christ. Since Christ has united Himself to us in the *incarnation*, we can be united to Him *by the Holy Spirit*. In itself, the incarnation of the Son of God does not unite us to Him, for by itself it does not accomplish salvation. Christ united to Himself a human nature, not the nature of the elect---as though the elect had a separate humanity different from the rest of the human race.

On the other hand, there can be *no atonement without incarnation*. Jesus needed to do this as man, as human, for *it was man* who had sinned in the very first place. It was *in our nature* that Christ offered Himself to the Father on the cross, and *in our nature* that He ascended far above all things created, and *in our nature* that Christ lives and reigns forever---in unbroken personal union.

Therefore, *the incarnation is more than the basis for this union*, as though the union or something else, separate and inherently disconnected. The complete identification of the eternal Son with our flesh and blood is part of our union with Him. Christ's union with us, in the incarnation, is the *foundation* for our union with Him, both now and in the eternal future. So the incarnation should not be seen as *merely a means to salvation*. Rather, salvation finds its *ultimate fulfillment* in the union of humanity with God seen in the incarnate Christ.

As mentioned before in the previous analogy; electricity lines may go past the house, but to benefit from the electricity supply, the house *must be connected* to the lines. If the house is not connected to the power grid, the house and consequent occupants of that house, cannot possibly benefit from the heat and light that electricity generates to our comfort. To be united to Christ, we need to be connected to Christ *by the Holy Spirit through faith*. Moreover, without electricity searching through the power grid, the house could have no benefit, even if the wires were connected. In a like manner, if Christ were not incarnate and had not, in our flesh, rendered satisfaction to God's justice on the cross, there would be absolutely nothing to deliver us from sin and the just and holy wrath of God. Thus, both the incarnate Christ and the Holy Spirit together, *distinctively but indivisibly*, bring about our union with Christ.

Union with Christ and Soteriology

Today, there are number ongoing theological conversations, primarily from the realm of academic theology; regarding the primary umbrella under which the New Testament places its doctrine of salvation as "union with Christ" (Lints, 2012, p. 283). Being united to Christ is the "key" to understand the variegated ways that salvation plays out. That "union" can be understood in a multitude of ways: as a **union by faith** (by faith believers are united to Christ), as a **relational union** (have any personal relationship with Christ), as a **mystical union** (believers are

united to Christ in the Spirit), as an **ontological union** (believers share in the divine nature), as a **cosmic victory union** (over the powers of darkness that unites believers to Christ), as a **legal union** with Christ (by which He suffers the punishment owing to sinners that they in turn are legally accounted innocent), as a **familial union** (been adopted into the family of God), or as a **covenant union** (believers are brought into covenant with God). In other words, there are a host of contexts in which the New Testament uses the language of being "in Christ."

Michael Horton helpfully writes, "The theme of union with Christ *brings together* the temporal tenses of our salvation---past, present, and future---as well as the objective and subjective, historical and existential, corporate and individual, forensic and transformative, and a unilateral gift that establishes a reciprocal relationship of faith speaking and answering the covenant as a *nucleus cosmic renewal*" (Horton, 2007, p. 131).

In articulating this reality of "union," this "key" is indeed rich and profound enough to justify many diverse facets to be illuminated. In mapping modern theology, the emphasis upon union with Christ has often been framed over and against imputation and infusion. When union with Christ is understood in distinction from relational and transformationist soteriologies, the consequent notion of salvation is referred to as participationist.

An influential representative of contemporary participationist soteriology is the New Finnish school. Its central voice, *Tuoma Mannermaa*, has argued passionately that Luther himself was far more interested in participationist accounts of soteriology, in which "union with Christ" was central, that had previously been allowed (Mannermaa, 2005, p. 74). Calvin likewise has come under critical scrutiny in recent decades indicating that his loyalty to the "mystical" union at the heart of salvation was far greater than his commitment to the forensic features of justification. Nevertheless, it is vital to reckon with the way in which contemporary discussion of "union" language has forged strange new alliances modern theology, wherein Luther is regarded in some circles as closer to Eastern Orthodoxy than he is to Protestant orthodoxy, and Calvin is

pitted against the Reformed tradition. These interpretations of the Protestant Performers concern us only insofar as eliminate the map of soteriology in the contemporary context (Muller, 2000).

Whatever else Christ does on the sinner's behalf, it happens by being brought into vital union with Christ in order that the dynamic benefits of His life, death, and resurrection pass on to us, *not just at the end of life, but now in our Christian life*. Earlier in this paper this persisting question was raised, *"How do these benefits "pass on" to believers?"*

Both participationist and forensic accounts of salvation start with the assumption that *God is the one from whom salvation begins*, and that the originating intentions of salvation have to do with the divine character as opposed to salvation being a "Plan B" after the apparent "mistake" of human sin and corruption. To put it simply, the eternal God is the starting point for *all salvation*. It is God who saves; it is His creatures that are saved. This location of Creator origination, in the nature and character of salvation, in God in the first place, protects salvation from becoming a human project in which God may or may not participate.

Even though we have surveyed the following topics, in relationship to other perspectives, it behooves us to make another "theological sweep" of these topics from the mapping point of soteriology and union with Christ.

Eastern Orthodoxy

Thus far, we have firmly established the proposition that Eastern Orthodox soteriology unequivocally affirms that humans participate *quite literally* in the "divine life," otherwise known as "theosis." Understandably, they do not take on the full range of divine attributes, but rather "share" in the actual divine life of the Triune God. This is often referred to as "deification."

Athanasius's famous words serve as an important touchstone of the doctrine (Hardy, 1995, p. 54), "*He [the Word of God] became human that we might become God.*" In Christ, the fullness of the *divine life is interwoven* with the fully constituted human nature. In the incarnation, the divine life is "shared" with humanity. The incarnation serves as the eternal intention of the creative act of God and fulfillment of the original creation of humankind. "Theosis" is not so much the solution to the problem of the fall of mankind, but rather the goal of creation from the very beginning. God created the world to unite it to Himself.

The significance of the Eastern Orthodoxy points to theosis as an *ontological or metaphysical change*, due to the fact that humans share in the divine Being of God Himself, as opposed to merely being acquitted in a divine courtroom, the essence of the Reformation's "justification by faith" paradigm. Humans literally *take on something essential to God*---namely His life. Yet, it is precisely at this point, that the historical center of controversy between the East and the West most often ensues. The ontological claim of theosis (participation in the divine) often carries a Neoplatonic cast whereby the creature takes on *actual characteristics* of the Creator, and the distinction between creature and Creator is minimized.

This suggests that there is little fundamental, ontological chasm between creature and Creator. On this rendering, the Western churches (Protestant and Catholic) parted company with Eastern Orthodoxy. Protestants more often have interpreted "union with Christ" as a union that is **covenantal** (i.e. inclusion) or **legal** (i.e. acquittal), or **familial** (i.e. adoption). Roman Catholics have tended to think of union language is pointing toward a moral union (i.e. righteousness). What Eastern Orthodoxy shares with Roman Catholicism on this point is the actual transformation of humans as the ground of their union with God in Christ.

Protestants have been very cautious about these ontological and casual grammars expressing the realities of salvation in Christ.

"Is the actual transformation of believers prior to or antecedent to their union with Christ? Is the ground of union to be found in the transformations of believers or in the declarations of God?"

In an attempt to protect the Creator/creature distinction, the Eastern Orthodox Church is seeking to revive and defend the over distinction between the divine energies and the divine essence. For example, *the divine essence* is God's *immutable characteristics* that are not shared in any way with His creatures. God's *energies* refer to *His actions* in the world. They are not something that exists apart from God. They are *God Himself* as He reveals Himself to us. The creatures are able to know God not in *His divine essence*, but rather because of *His divine actions*. These actions are manifestations of God Himself in direct relationship to His creation.

When persons are "saved" they are saved by a direct experience of God Himself. They come into full contact with God Himself, and His life becomes their life. They are not deified in the sense that they take on God's essence. This remains always hidden to them and in assessable. Rather, the takeoff God's energies and they are deified in this sense. Everything God revealed of Himself (the divine energies) and economy of salvation is disclosed and the incarnation of Christ and is that which every true Christian inherits. The fullness of God's life and the human nature of Jesus is the very same life in which every genuine Christian shares. This is the inherent meaning of (2 Peter 1:4---which affirms that believers "become partakers of God's divine nature."

What are the key differences between this conception of salvation in Eastern Orthodoxy and that of Western Christianity?

Eastern Orthodoxy wants to see the grace of salvation is an *extension* in the presence of God in creation. Western Christianity (both Protestant and Catholic) has conceived of the grace of salvation is in operation of God *distinct* from the acts of God in creating the world. Eastern traditions of thought of salvation is on a *continuum* with creation, whereas the Western traditions of tended to think of salvation as a *distinctly different* sort of divine action from creation. Protestant orthodoxy has tended to think, in accord with the Eastern traditions that the economy of salvation is *not in the first place about transformations of believers*, but rather about their relationship to God. Catholics, in accord with the Eastern traditions, have thought about the relationship of the church to God as an *ontological or metaphysical fashion*, rather than declarative or legal. Western Christendom has also thought of Christ's death and resurrection as the *divine act of salvation*, whereas the Eastern Church has thought of Christ incarnation as the *defining act of salvation*.

Eastern Orthodox Bishop Calisto Ware concludes;

"The cross is essential, but it can only be understood in the light of what goes before--- Christ taking up into Himself our entire human nature at His birth---and likewise in the light of what comes afterwards, the resurrection, ascension and Second Coming. Any theology of salvation that concentrates narrowly on the cross, at the expense of the resurrection, is bound to be unbalanced to Orthodoxy" (Ware, 1994, p. 121).

Union with Christ in His Sufferings

Because of the inclusive nature of union with Christ, we are intimately connected with not only the glorious resurrection aspects of salvation, but *also the painful, crucifixion elements* as well. The apostle Paul expressed the fervent desire to be conformed to Christ in the likeness of His death (Philippians 3:10), "that I may know Him and the power of His resurrection, and may *share His sufferings, becoming like Him in His death.*"

From what immediate context was Paul writing this from to the church at Philippi? Without question, one that none of us would willingly desire to be in, that is for sure. When Paul wrote this, he knew, all too well, his immediate circumstances. He was languishing away in a Roman prison, awaiting trial, with the possibility of execution. He actually did not expect to be sentenced to death; rather he anticipated a future ministry of continued fruitfulness. The fact is he was eventually released and did enjoy an extended period of apostolic service for his final imprisonment, trial, and execution.

However, at the time Paul wrote this, he could not have known of these future events, and so his condition when he wrote these words was grim, at best. We know from history that Roman prisons were places suffering. Paul knew, throughout his ministry, that Jesus had suffered. Continually, especially before the coming of the Holy Spirit on Pentecost, His disciples were not only chronically unreliable, but appeared to continually misunderstand not only who Jesus was, but what His mission was all about, especially in regards to the cross. But, even more than that, Jesus faced adversity every day. He was confronted by the hugely hypocritical, Jewish religious authorities, who are constantly seeking ways to have Him murdered. He was encountering all kinds of individuals, steeped in a life of sin, Judaism had all but forgotten, much less even cared to reach out to. Everywhere Jesus turned, He was doing miracles of healing and deliverance. The devil harassed Jesus with difficult temptation after temptation, even up to the final moment on the cross, and the very last gasp of air exhaling, "*Father, into Your hands do I commit My spirit*" (Luke 23:46). Jesus' ministry remained physically draining, emotionally exhausting and spiritually challenging, at every turn, with every step, leading closer and closer to his rendezvous with destiny in Jerusalem and the cross event.

It is very possible that, because Christ was pulled in so many different competing directions, had if He Himself sought His identity with His Heavenly Father, the stress alone would have likely proved detrimental to the redemptive goal of the cross, for our sakes.

If there is ever the slightest doubt as to whether or not Paul also wrestled with similar adversity and suffering, in his ministry and in his union with Christ, his quote here in (2 Corinthians 11:12-33) should settle all arguments;

"Five times I received at the hands of the Jews the 40 lashes less one. Three times I was beaten with rods. Once I was stoned. Three times I was shipwrecked; a night and a day I was adrift at sea; on frequent journeys, and danger from rivers, danger from robbers, danger from my own people, danger from Gentiles, danger in the city, danger in the wilderness, dangerous sea, danger from Paul's brothers; and toil and hardship, through many a sleepless night, in hunger and thirst, often without food, in cold exposure. And, apart from other things, there is the daily pressure on me of my anxiety for all the churches. Who is weak, am I not weak?" (vv. 24-29)

While it is true that none of us are the Apostle Paul's clone, these factors are, in some measure, common to all who are united to Christ. Jesus suffered because of who He is; we suffer because we are one with Him. In fact, we are called to this (Philippians 1:29). There is suffering that automatically goes along with being human in a fallen world, because of our solidarity as descendants of Adam; the deterioration and decay of our physical bodies in the aging process, the many sicknesses or disabilities that plague us, young, at the prime of life, or in old age. And, this only the beginning of our woes as a member of the human race. How about the tragedies, griefs, frustrations, disappointments, betrayal by those we trusted, abuse from bullies, slander from the ignorant, irrational opposition and uncaring injustice from elected leaders drunk with power, the growing demoralization and paganism of America, the passing of gender laws clearly in shameless, blatant opposition to God's will, the continual, shocking, senseless acts of violence which victimize the innocent, fanatical international terrorism from radical Muslims shooting up American citizens in our country, the racism from blacks and whites, our unrelenting economic

fears of future collapse, etc.? In addition to these, there's the ever-increasing, marginalization, slander and even persecution of sincere Christians from a godless world in gloating, active disobedience to and defiance of Almighty God, Creator of heaven and earth.

Over and above all of that, as Christian believers in general, there is also the particular opposition and adversity toward ministers and other called individuals serving in some kind of ministry be it in church, in teaching, or ministering in some other way which reflects the various gifts of the Spirit Paul outlined in his epistles. There is opposition to our ministries, sometimes for good reason, but more often than not from self-centeredness and willful unbelief of those who mock God. We face the skepticism and rejection of the gospel, sometimes worse, complete indifference to it. We encounter hypocrisy in the church from professing Christians who are anything but sincere with God as they bear the fruits of contradiction between profession and practice. We patiently work with immature, baby Christians who constantly require "baby food" and sometimes make us wonder if they are authentic believers to start with. We, ourselves, are especially targeted by real, demonic forces and spiritual enemies of (Ephesians 6) for temptations from the world, flesh and devil, in hopes to discourage us or entangle us in some sort of scandal and bring shipwreck to our ministries and shame to the good name of Christ. There are those Christians, especially in Third World countries, which face inevitable imprisonment for their faithfulness to Christ, often with torture and eventual death. Many Christians are martyred cruelly each year by scores of adversaries beyond ISIS. In comparison, Paul says much the same in (2 Corinthians 4:8-12), "We are afflicted in every way . . . perplexed . . . persecuted . . . struck down. . . Always carrying in the body the death of Jesus. . . We who live are always being given over to death for Jesus sake. . . Death is at work in us."

These are sobering thoughts for those who are actively serving the Lord, but they are the reality we face every day. Before we cave into questioning our call, we need to understand that while we do personally share in the death of Jesus, through our union with Him, by God's grace, God compensates our challenges with His gracious strength and provision from the Spirit we require staying in the race of faith. *"While we are afflicted, we are not crushed; we are not driven to despair; we are not forsaken; we are not destroyed; for the life of Jesus is manifest (now) in our bodies"* (2 Corinthians 4:7-12). In Romans, Paul straightaway announces that all of our sufferings, *"of the present time are to be considered insignificant in comparison with God's future glory awaiting us"* (Romans 8:18). Moreover, in (2 Corinthians 4:17), *"This slight momentary affliction [stressing its lightness and temporal nature] in contrast to God's eternal weight of glory is beyond comparison."* In (Philippians 3:10), Paul's desire is to share the sufferings of Christ so that he might know *"the power of His resurrection."*

Paul's own experience of suffering provides a valuable model for us by which we might appreciate how suffering derives from participation with Christ. Paul interpreted his suffering through the lens of participation in the death of Christ. He regarded suffering as a *normal part* of the Christian experience. Since *every Christian* is brought into fellowship with the suffering of Christ in *baptism*, we can hardly disagree with Paul here. This twofold soteriological experience with Christ is summed up in two words---*death and resurrection*. Paul was careful not to miss the connection between suffering and life, whereas by God's power Jesus's death led to His resurrection, so also God brings life from death in the personal experience of the believer. Gorman expresses a similar notion while emphasizing the significance of the "co-prefix" for understanding Paul's thoughts on union with Christ: "If we co-suffer with Christ we are co-heirs with Him and will be co-glorified with Him (Gorman, 2001, p. 22).

All of this leads us to the conclusion that, in light of the fact we are sharing in the death and resurrection of Christ, this reality significantly transcends the mere status of the believer with respect to salvation. The Christian is operating in true "*resurrection-power*" eclipsing even their new positional status in union with Christ. He is continually "being conformed as he is sharing the sufferings of Christ." Therefore, regarding the issue of suffering in union with Christ, all of suffering, regardless of the form or intensity it may take, should be viewed as our *personal* participation in Christ, not merely an *imitation* of Christ. Believer share in the ongoing force of Christ death and the power of His resurrection, and one consequence of that is that all of the elect will undergo suffering in their union with Christ.

What else is Paul trying to tell us here? A critical truth we should remind ourselves every single day, as believers, and that is, there are dangers in focusing too much on the glories that await us, if that leads us to unrealistically discount the reality of present sufferings. If we intend to share the glories of Christ, if we are being transformed from one degree of glory to another, being made partakers of God's divine nature, that there is absolutely no detour around the equally pertinent reality that we will share also the sufferings of Christ. The cross precedes the crown always. This was Luther's contention on his corrective "theology of the cross" hermeneutic which, he believed, added balance to an overemphasis "theology of glory."

VI. Constantine Campbell on Union

In spite of the fact that union with Christ and justification is a hotly debated theological theme in Pauline studies today, there is never been a comprehensive exegetical Greek analysis of this theme within the Pauline canon, that is, until 2012. Constantine Campbell, Ph.D, a world-renowned theological scholar and senior lecturer in Greek and New Testament studies, at Moore Theological College in Sydney, Australia, finally accomplished this phenomenal task with the

first exegetical and theological investigation of union with Christ in Paul's letters, carefully examining every occurrence of the phrases "*in Christ*," "*with Christ*," "*through Christ*," "*into Christ*," and other related expressions, in the history of the church. His resource book, entitled, "*Paul and Union with Christ*" is nearly 480 pages long (Campbell, 2012).

A paper on union with Christ would be not be complete unless some findings were not briefly noted. In an attempt to "exercise the art of brevity," this discussion will be limited to the documentation of major conclusions resulting from his extensive research into union with Christ, from a Pauline perspective.

Major Conclusions of His Study

Outlining the implications of his study, first, the term "union with Christ" is deemed insufficient to convey all that Paul includes in the theme. To do justice to the full spectrum of Paul's thought and language, the terms *union*, *participation*, *identification*, and *incorporation* are adopted. These four umbrella terms successfully capture the full range of prepositional phraseology, metaphorical conceptualizations and theological interactions that Paul draws on to communicate what he means to be united to Christ. Some of the characteristics of the meta-theme of union, participation, identification, and incorporation include locality, instrumentality, trinitarianism, eschatology, and spiritual reality. Secondly, the meta-theme of union, participation, identification, and incorporation is regarded to be of utmost importance to Paul, yet *does not* occupy the "center" of his theological framework. It is rather, the essential ingredient that binds all other theological elements together.

Summary of Metaphorical Language

One of Paul's most powerful tools for describing the spiritual reality of union with Christ is his selection of particular metaphors. The metaphor of the *body of Christ* depicts the church as an organic being as each member partakes in Christ and his join one to another. The metaphor implies union by its very nature. The metaphors of *temple and building* convey the corporate nature of the church, with the *temple* depicting the dwelling of God by His Spirit among His people, and the *building* denoting a structure incorporated into Christ, its foundation. The metaphor of *marriage* profoundly depicts the churches spiritual union with Christ as a personal and exclusive bond as He saves, prepares, and cares for her, while she submits to His headship. The metaphor of *clothing* depicts the reality of conversion to Christ as well as its attendant ethical expectations; the believer *has put on Christ* and *is to put on Christ*. It is a symbol for union with Christ that entails *conformity to Christ*.

Conclusions Regarding Christian Living

Virtually every aspect of the Christian life *is informed* in some way by believers union with Christ. The *status and identity* that believers enjoy, which is so programmatic for Paul's ethical framework and instruction, are inextricably bound up with union with Christ. From there flow the activities and characteristics of believers, which again are *intertwined with union* with Christ. The Christian life is so weaved at the fabric of union with Christ that the most appropriate moniker for believers is "*in Christ*."

Living Out the Death and Resurrection of Christ

Participating with Christ in the events of His death and resurrection continue to give their stamp to the life of the believer, for he continues to participate in the death and resurrection of

Christ in his daily life, whether he is conscious of this or not. The Christian life correlates to the "moral" sense of dying and rising with Christ that is illustrated in (Romans 6). That is, believers *must make an intentional effort to die to sin in their day-to-day experience*. In other words, dying with Christ involves not only participation in the historical event of His death, but also in the daily battle against one's own personal sins, for which Christ died for in the first place.

Furthermore, the solemn responsibility of believers is walking in the newness of life that comes from sharing in the resurrection of Christ. Resurrection brings about a *completely new life*, a *powerful new dynamo*, and being conformed to Christ, especially in His resurrection, as expressed in our concrete daily living of that new life.

Realistically, there will always be apparent eschatological tension in the framework of Paul's thinking when it comes to sharing in the death and resurrection of Christ. On the one hand, believers *have already* died and risen with Christ, Participating with Him in the particular events of salvation history. On the other hand, believers *are to live out* the death and resurrection of Jesus in their lives, as the significance of their personal sharing in His historical death and resurrection taking hold of controlling the schema of everyday living. The believer *continually* dies with Christ. It is an *ongoing manifestation* of an affirmation of his past death with Christ. The actual reality of this eschatological tension means that believers who become united to Christ in His death and resurrection may not appear any different in the first instance; rather, their conformity to Christ must unfold with increasing significance in the progress and growth of their relationship with Christ. Only God knows our hearts enough to determine that.

It cannot be denied that something very real has actually changed for the person who dissipates with Christ in His death and resurrection, and yet outwardly the profound significance of this change may not be immediately obvious.

Since the purpose of Christ's death was "ethical-religious," the implications therefore of participating with Christ and His death follows suit: that is why the *mystical fellowship* with Christ is not complete until it becomes the *ethical-religious relationship*. Such reasoning will avoid a common problem afflicting modern believers who may struggle to see a clear rationale for holy living when they understand that reconciliation with God *is to the work of Christ*, not according to their works. Since salvation is by grace, the importance of righteous living can be muted in the name of avoiding moralism or legalism.

It is the "*life-narrative*" of Christ which believers are conformed to. In other words, because death and resurrection were what Christ experienced---indeed, the necessary "path"---believers are to be conformed to is that *same narrative*. This pattern transcends merely imitation of Christ; the word "*cruciformity*" better encapsulates the inherent meaning Paul is seeking to convey. This is an ongoing pattern of living in Christ and of dying with Him that produces a Christlike cruciform person. Cruciform is what it is like for Christ indwelling him and him indwelling in Christ. It is a unilateral paradigm with immense implications for Christian living. To be united to Christ is to be a "living exegesis" of this narrative of Christ. The believer is not simply retracing the steps of Christ, but participating in His work in a manner that is expressed in the believer's life. This point must not be missed; the believers are both actively partaking in the historic events of salvation while also living them out in his or her own contemporary time and experience. This is Paul's "spirituality of cruciformity" seen in (Philippians 2:6-11).

Defining Union with Christ

In spite of the many proposals for the definition of union with Christ, the author suggests that the best theme find itself expressed in four terms; *union, dissipation, identification and incorporation*.

Union gathers up faith union with Christ, mutual indwelling, Trinitarian, and nuptial notions. *Participation* conveys partaking in the events of Christ's narrative. *Identification* refers to the believer's location in the realm of Christ and their allegiance to His Lordship.

Incorporation denotes the corporate dimensions of membership in the body of Christ. Taken together, these four themes function as the "umbrella" of concepts which cover the full spectrum of Pauline language, ideas, and things that are bound up in the meta-theme of union with Christ.

VII. Summary

My hope is that the preceding pages, of this Capstone paper, has presented a unique theological vision that blends the best two words; strange and familiar in relation to our union with Christ. Optimistically, this vision, written about here, barely skims the surface of possibilities of understanding and applying this historic doctrine to praxis today. The dualism and individualism of our age, that has particularly affected Western churches, is seeking to dull the significance of this profound teaching. As a result, our spiritual eyesight can become colored by these idols of modernity that the language of union with Christ is reduced to self-help strategies to make us feel good about ourselves and therefore minimize the heavenly truth of intimate, loving communion with God, a sense of God's majestic transcendence or some other synchrony seeking to take our eyes off the person of Christ and the work of God's salvation for us.

In light of America's cultural captivity today, I maintain we do not need to simply re-create a new set of propositions for our theology. We need a brand-new set of eyes, a new vision, a new way to begin to sense our cultural captivity and received the Spirit's Word, for this hour and time in history, to the church through Scripture. In several places of this paper I made mention of the critical need to implement a theological strategy of retrieval to address our current cultural and spiritual realities where postmodernism, skepticism toward Scriptural authority,

relativism toward ethics and increasing paganism is threatening our world with destructive, foundational change for the future, if the present trends continue.

Union with Christ should not only mystify us, but seem so strange that it shakes our theological presuppositions to the bone. Yet, at the same time, ironically, it should also be as warm and inviting as a family reunion. The reason why is because union with Christ is God's choice to orient us to conform to the same Jesus Christ to Christians have already been united by the Spirit.

To revisit our Christian past is a "back to the future" journey that, if done with an open heart, will reveal our contemporary shortcomings we are not even aware of, in order that we might reevaluate not only what are doing in the church, but why we are doing it. Our thinking will inevitably be challenged, but all for the better. Our grand faith heritage has the potential to expose our limitations and simultaneously challenge the modern categories that squeeze the gospel and its own mold and renew the theological imagination, by shedding new light on the Scriptural witness. Or, in other words, seeing with new eyes does not point to end of the conversation but to change in the theological conversation by exposing "the blind spots" we naturally cannot see because we are right in the middle of them all. In some ways, this is like the shock of cross-cultural missions; it has way of showing us what and who we really are rather than ignoring a deficiency that, if left unchecked, could become a major crisis.

The functional deism of Western culture assumes that salvation is more about maintaining a faith commitment or being "good and nice." In direct contrast to this, union with Christ is nothing less than a new, adopted identity in which God's good creation is restored. Union with Christ gives us our true identities and removes us from the center of the drama where the triune God is actually the real central actor and we participate in this cosmic drama united to

Jesus Christ by the Spirit. In observing the sacraments of the church, seeking a vibrant devotional life of daily prayer and Bible study, joyfully participating in worship, ministry and fellowship activities in our local church, cheerfully engaging in good works towards those in need, and faithfully practicing time-tested disciplines for spiritual formation, we can cultivate and deepen the reality and appreciation for what God has done for us in union with Christ. In addition, these activities performed, and a holy love for Christ, will check the spiritual corruption of the functional deism which is seeking to push the Trinity and union with Christ to the sidelines of the church.

As we seek to intentionally meditate on the magnificent truths of union with Christ, this action will *inform* our thinking in order that we may be *conformed* to the image of Christ with a more *transformed* mindset which reflects God's glory in dazzling and amazing new ways to a lost world all around us. To this end, I prayerfully submit this paper, to the glory of God.

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